

Study of Fourier Transform Signal Processing

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Abstract :

Mathematics is everywhere in the world. It is used in every field. Fourier transforms is one of the oldest and a well-known technique in the field of mathematics and engineering mathematical work. In this paper, we have studied the Fourier transform, its uses the signal processing forms and the making of the mobile phone. It is very important for the modern world for the easier solution of the problems.

Introduction :

The signals are improved and being processed by using the proposed transformation. PQDs are inherently non-stationary and require simultaneous time-frequency analysis. Some popular techniques [1-5] are used for PQ analysis and they are: Short-time Fourier transforms, Gabor transforms, Hilbert-Huang transforms, Kalman filters, parametric methods, Wavelet transform and Stock well

transform. Fourier analysis is also being termed as spectral analysis or Harmonic analysis, decomposes a time-dependent periodic phenomenon into a series of sinusoidal wave functions, each one is defined by an unique amplitude and phase values. Fourier transform converts complex curves into sum of a series of cosine waves and an additive term. Each wave is being defined by unique amplitude and a phase angle, where the amplitude value is half the height of a wave, and the phase angle defines the offset between the origin and the peak of the wave in between the range of 0 to 2π . Each term determines the number of complete cycles completed by the wave over the defined interval. Some harmonic terms are being added to produce a complete complex curve and component curve, and accounts for a percentage of the total variance in the original complex curve. Fourier analysis has been used in digital image and processing of image and for analysis of a single image into a two-dimensional wave form, and more recently has been used for magnetic resonance imaging, angiographic assessment, automated lung segmentation & image quality assessment and Mobile stethoscope. Fourier transforms which is also used in frequency domain representation. Fourier analysis used as time series analysis proved its application in Quantum mechanics; Signal processing, Image Processing and filters, representation, Data Processing and Analysis and many more. Fourier transforms are obviously very essential to conduct of Fourier spectroscopy, and that alone would justify its importance.

Fourier transforms are very vital in other pursuits as well; such as electrical signal analysis, diffraction, optical testing, optical processing, imaging, holography, and also for remote sensing. Thus, knowledge of Fourier transforms can be a springboard to many other fields. The main idea behind Fourier transform is that a function of direct time can be expressed as a complex valued function of reciprocal space, that is, frequency. The Fourier Transform is a mathematical procedure which transforms a function present in the time domain to the frequency domain.

Formulation :

Fourier Transform is a mathematical method which uses the trigonometric functions to transform a time domain into a frequency domain spectrum. It is also called the frequency domain representation of the original signals. The Fourier transform of a function ' f ' is being denoted by providing a circumflex f . There are

many common conventions for defining the Fourier transform of an integral function. Here we will provide the following definition, i.e.

$$f(\xi) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x)e^{-2\pi i x \xi} dx$$

For real number ' ξ ', the reason for the negative sign convention in the exponent is that in electrical engineering, it is common to use to represent a signal with zero initial phase and frequency ξ_0 , which may be positive or negative.

The negative sign convention causes the product to be 1 (frequency zero) when causing the integral to diverge. The result is a Dirac delta function at $\xi = \xi_0$, exactly what we want since this is the only frequency component of the sinusoidal signal. Variable x represents time which is independent in nature; the transform variable ξ represents frequency (for example if the time is measured in seconds, then the frequency is in terms of hertz). Under certain conditions, f is being determined via the inverse transform, i.e.

$$f(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\xi)e^{2\pi i x \xi} d\xi$$

for any real number x . The sum of two functions which is equal to the sum of their individual transforms.

$$f\{f(x) + g(x)\} = F(Y) + G(Y)$$

Thus, in LSI system the sum of signal in a spectrum can be provided by simply adding together their individual spectra.

If,

$$f\{f(\xi)\} = F(x)$$

then,

$$f\{F(x)\} = f(-\xi)$$

The Fourier transform of a convolution is provided by the product of their individual transforms.

$$f\{f(x) * g(x)\} = F(\xi)g(\xi)$$

The Fourier Transform of a product is completed by the convolution of their individual transforms, i.e.

$$f\{f(x)g(x)\} = F(\xi) * g(\xi)$$

Types of Fourier Transform :

There are mainly four different forms of Fourier Transform, which are classified below :

- A periodic continuous signal, continuous and a periodic spectrum. This is the general form of continuous time Fourier Transforms.
- Discrete a periodic spectrum and periodic continuous signal.

Results and Discussion :

Mathematics is everywhere used, almost in every phenomenon, technology, observations, and experiments, etc. All we need to do is to understand the logic hidden behind the provided question, solution is being provided by mathematics. Since mathematical calculation provides us a way to the ultimate results of every experiment, it becomes quite easy to analyze those calculations before concluding. The present era of communication and technology has provided us some major catalysts in developing the modern human society. Communication involves automatic transmission of the data through wires and radio circuits through signals.

In communication systems, signal processing, and electrical engineering, signals are the function that transfer the information about the behavior or attributes of certain phenomenon. Signals are basically a mean to transmit information in accordance with certain pre-arranged system. It includes audio, video, speech, images, communication, geophysical, sonar, radar, medical and musical signals and many more. One of the most important communication devices in modern era, the Cell Phones is dramatically changing the typical system of people interaction and communication with each other. Cell phones emits very small amount of electromagnetic signals via their radio waves through a low power transmitter provided in cell phone. The cell phone has being designed by using a lot of mathematics in just about every aspect of their design. Also mobile phones operate by principles of electromagnetic, which are described mathematically.

- Person has to dial a number that it is based on a protocol which is named as Internet Protocol (IP). Protocol is nothing but a basic a set of mathematical rules.
- The phone has to use the coordinates for the location of the Satellite to receive and transmit other end.
- Then they have to convert from a wave system into a voice system that it is based in alphabetical words, and then again translated between the two system based in a numerical system called binary.
- This binary system is integrated into the satellites; transmitter and receivers by the motherboard integrated in each system, then incorporated into each system through programming and all being traversed by mathematics. By the mean of binary system it is multiple of 2's, and they goes by the 0's and 1's and it is also called machine language because those machines only work with electric impulses which are On and Off.

The principle of the Fourier transform in this case is that any signal, such that the produces sound by a musical instrument, example- piano, violin, trumpet, and drum. Any type of sound recording which is being recorded can be expressed as the sum of a collection of sine and cosine waves with different frequencies and amplitudes.

This collection of waves can be manipulated with relative ease for example, allowing a recording to be compressed. This Fourier decomposition lives at the heart of modern electronic music- a synthesizer combine pure sine and cosine tone to reproduce the diverse sounds of instruments, both naturally as well as artificial, according to Fourier general prescription. Anyone who is being marveled at the small size of an MP3 files compared with the same recording which is not being compressed form has seen the power of the Fourier transform at work. The Fourier Transform is an algorithm used in different type of functions, including signal processing and statistical applications across a broad range of applications.

Our mobile phone is device performing Fourier Transformations. Every mobile device network, notebook, tablet, and phones have been built for high-speed cellular data connections, just like Fourier Transform. The Fourier Transform is a method for doing this process very efficiently.

Conclusion :

The idea behind Fourier transform is that a function of direct space can be expressed equivalently as a complex valued function of reciprocal space that is frequency sometimes called Fourier space. The proposed Fourier transform has a wide range of help in various domains like power distribution system, wireless, signal processing, cell phone manufacturing, mechanical and industrial application.

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